

VARIETAL INFLUENCE OF MANGO CULTIVARS ON WEED DIVERSITY AND DENSITY IN MANGO ORCHARD.

Adeoye, P. O. and S. O. S. Akinyemi

National Horticultural Research Institute, P. M. B. 5432, Idi-Ishin, Ibadan, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

In a 25-year old mango orchard at the National Horticultural Research Institute, Idi-Ishin, Ibadan, a field study was carried out in July, 2009 to assess the diversities, distribution and densities of weed species with preference to the architectural configuration of the test crop. Two varieties of mango, Edward and Saigon were used for the study. Three uniform size trees of each variety were selected to serve as replicate and each variety was replicated three times. The results indicated that more weed species thrive well under Saigon than Edward. Out of the 16 weed species found only 9 were found under Edward. The total population of weeds in the studied unit were 1888 out of which 1172 (90.6%) were broad leaves and 176 (9.4%) were grasses as no sedge was found in the survey. The highest weed relative density was observed for *Tridax procumbens* (81.15) under Edward while 46.51 was observed under Saigon and the lowest relative density of 0.33 was observed for *Cnetis ferruginea*, *Combretum hispidum* and *Chromolaena odorata* under Saigon and 0.17 being recorded for *Cnetis ferruginea* under Edward. The diversity indices are 1.481 and 1.491 for Saigon and Edward respectively.

KEYWORDS: Mango, weed diversity, weed density.

INTRODUCTION

Mango (*Mangifera indica*) belongs to the family, Anacardiaceae. It is indigenous to India, widely cultivated in many tropical and subtropical regions and one of the most extensively exploited fruits for food, juice, flavour fragrance and colour. It is an outstanding source of vitamin A and a good source of vitamin C apart from the normal minerals and other vitamins (Sadhu, 1999). Mango leaves and barks are used traditionally to cure malaria. Sadhu (1999) also noted that mango leaves are used ritually as floral decorations at wedding and religious occasions in India. The trees are large, erect, mulch branched with crown radius of 10m. The leaves are evergreen alternate and simple.

Weeds adversely affect crop growth and eventually lead to reduced yield in all crops. In West Africa, weeds are common sight and their control is a major factor causing yield decline (Wilson, 1987). Weeds are major problems of plantation crops especially at their early stage.

Plant canopy especially in plantation crops has a great influence on light transmission which determines the rate of weed distribution and species especially in plantation crops. The total supply of light to the land is the most reliable of the several environmental resources required for plant growth and in contrast to water and nutrients, light cannot be stored for later use; it must be used when received or it is lost forever (Donald, 1963). Light varies in duration, intensity and quality. Neighbouring plants may reduce light supply by direct interception. Leaves are the sight of light competition and those leaves that first intercept light may reflect it, absorb it, convert it to photosynthetic products, heat or transmit it (Zimdahl, 1993). Plants with large leaf area indices have a competitive advantage and normally override plants with smaller leaf areas. A plant's ability to intercept light is influenced by its angle of inclination and leaf arrangement. Plant with horizontal leaves are more competitive for light than those with upright leaves, plants with opposite leaves are less competitive than those with alternate, plants that are tall or erect have a competitive advantage over short, prostrate plants and a heavily shaded plants suffers reduced photosynthesis, leading to poor growth, a smaller root system, a reduced capacity for water or mineral uptake. The effect of shading is independent of direct competition for water or nutrients entirely under the influence of light (Ghafar and Watson, 1983). Studies in India (Shetty, *et al* 1982) have shown that dicots are shade sensitive than monocots and help explain why monocots are often important tropical weeds. Weeds are generally abundant in cultivated land and are subject to changes either in abundance or in weed species present in a locality over a period of time (Yakubu *et al.*, 2006). The National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT) is situated in the south western part of Nigeria where climate favours weed

germination and growth almost all the year round. (Futch and Singh, 2007) noted that weeds compete with citrus trees for water, light, space and harbour pathogens, rodents and also reduce the efficiency of orchard operations. About 30-40% of total fruit production cost is taken up by weed control. Indicating that weed management is a high cost factor in horticultural production (Usoroh, 1991). Recent studies have shown that weed shift occur in continuously cultivated land which may be as a result of high tillage practice, cropping systems, weed control and other changes in habitat (Smith and Akinde, 2000; Olorunmaiye and Olorunmaiye, 2008; Olorunmaiye and Olorunmaiye, 2009). In order to develop an appropriate weed control strategy(ies) for successive weed control programmes in the mango orchard, a good knowledge of weed type and composition is necessary. In essence this study is aimed at the critical observation of weed diversities and abundance as influenced by canopy configuration of the two dominant mango cultivars in the test orchard.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was carried out in the mango orchard of the National Horticultural Research Institute, Idi-Ishin, Ibadan. The orchard has been uniformly pruned twice in the last five years. Three uniform trees were picked to serve as replicate for each cultivar. To study the distribution of the weed species and their densities, a radius of 5m was marked eastward and westward from the base of each tree. Weeds were counted, described and collected within each of the 5 quadrat set at 1m on each radius. Two cultivars of mango, Saigon and Edward were considered in this study. 1m quadrat was used for the finding i. e. 5 quadrats east and 5 quadrats west of each sampled tree. Weed species in every quadrat were identified, counted, uprooted, weighed (fresh), oven dried and weighed.

Parameters taken from each quadrat were number of species, number of weeds (all species), fresh weight and weed dry matter. Weed dry matter was taken following the method of AOAC (1980). Data collected regarding number of weeds, fresh weight and weed dry matter were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using DMRT (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

Density and relative density of all weed species were computed according to Hussain (1989). Specie density was calculated as the number of individuals of a particular specie per unit area. Relative density which is the percentage value of density of a specie relative to the total density of all species is as expressed in the equation below;

$$\text{Relative Density} = d/D \times 100$$

Where d = density of a specie and D = density of all species.

Specie diversity was also calculated through Simpson Diversity Index, D which is a mathematical model that characterises species in a community. The proportion of specie *i* relative to the total number of species *P_i* is calculated and squared. The reciprocal of sum of squared proportions for all the species was taken through the formula below:

$$D = 1 / \sum P_i^2$$

Equitability or evenness was calculated using Simpson Index (D) as expressed below:

$$E_D = D/D_{MAX} = 1 / \sum P_i^2$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sixteen (16) weed species were identified in the sampled area for the study and are as classified and contained in Table 1. Out of the 16 species only 9 were found under Edward while all the 16 species were found under Saigon variety as shown in Table 2. From Table 2, the total number of weeds in the studied area is 1888 out of which 1172 (90.6%) were broad leaves and the remaining 176 (9.4%) were grasses while no sedge was found. Out of the 16 species identified only 9 were found under Edward but the total number of weeds found under the same variety was greater than that of Saigon as clearly seen in the table.

The highest weed relative density was observed for *Tridax procumbens* (81.15) under Edward while 46.51 was observed under Saigon and the lowest relative density of 0.33 was observed for *Cnetis ferruginea*, *Combretum hispidum* and *Chromolaena odorata* under Saigon and 0.17 being recorded for *Cnetis ferruginea* under

Edward as contained in Table 3. The diversity indices are 1.481 and 1.491 for Saigon and Edward respectively as shown in Table 4.

The relative effect of distance on number of weeds, fresh weight and dry weight are as seen in Table 4. It is revealed that more weeds are associated with Edward than Saigon. The studied unit was dominated by broadleaves and this could be attributed to the closed canopy which reduced light transmission. Distance from the base of sampled plants produced no definite pattern on the parameters taken as seen in Table 4 but there exist significant differences in Saigon variety with regards to the number of weeds, weed fresh weight and dry weight. This is as a result of irregular configuration of the canopies of the test stands. This study revealed that the number of weed species and their relative abundance varied across the cultivars in the orchard and this will go a long way in developing appropriate weed management method(s) as weed control is a function of weed floristic composition, density and distribution.

Table 1: Weed species found in the sampled area

Weed species	Family	Growth Form
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	Asteraceae	ABL
<i>Alchonea laxiflora</i>	Euphorbiaceae	PBL
<i>Althananthera sessilis</i>	Amaranthaceae	ABL
<i>Asystacia gangentica</i>	Acanthaceae	ABL
<i>Axonopus compressus</i>	Poaceae	AG
<i>Chromolaena odorata</i>	Euphorbiaceae	PBL
<i>Cnetis ferruginea</i>	Connaraceae	PBL
<i>Combretum hispidum</i>	Combretaceae	PBL
<i>Commelina diffusa</i>	Combretaceae	ABL
<i>Ficus exasperata</i>	Fabaceae	PBL
<i>Ipomoea involcrata</i>	Convolvulaceae	ABL
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Sapotaceae	PBL
<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Melastomataceae	ABL
<i>Panicum maximum</i>	Poaceae	PG
<i>Sida acuta</i>	Malvaceae	ABL
<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	Tiliaceae	ABL

ABL: Annual Broadleaf; AG: Annual Grass; PG: Perennial Grass; PBL: Perennial Broadleaf

Table 2: Density and relative density of weeds in the sampled area

Species	SAIGON			EDWARD		
	No. of weeds	Density	R. density	No. of weeds	Density	R. Density
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	22	0.73	3.40	0	0.00	0.00
<i>Alchonea laxiflora</i>	8	0.27	1.26	0	0.00	0.00
<i>Althananthera sessilis</i>	16	0.53	2.47	12	0.40	0.98
<i>Asystacia gangentica</i>	40	1.33	6.17	32	1.07	2.61
<i>Axonopus compressus</i>	84	2.80	13.02	58	1.98	4.71
<i>Chromolaena odorata</i>	2	0.07	0.33	0	0.00	0.00
<i>Cnetis ferruginea</i>	2	0.07	0.33	2	0.07	0.17
<i>Combretum hispidum</i>	2	0.07	0.33	0	0.00	0.00
<i>Commelina diffusa</i>	8	0.27	1.26	10	0.33	0.80
<i>Ficus exasperate</i>	2	0.07	0.33	6	0.20	0.49
<i>Ipomoea sp.</i>	64	2.13	9.91	28	0.93	2.27
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	12	0.40	0.40	0	0.93	6.80
<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	54	1.80	8.37	84	2.80	6.80
<i>Panicum maximum</i>	34	1.13	5.26	0	0.00	0.00
<i>Sida acuta</i>	8	0.27	1.26	0	0.00	0.00
<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	300	10.00	46.51	998	33.27	81.15
16	658	21.50	102.07	1230	41.00	99.98

The diversity index of weed species were calculated using Table 3.

Table 3 : Diversity index of weed species in the sampled area.

Weed species	SAIGON			EDWARD		
	No of weeds	Pi	Pi ²	No of weeds	Pi	Pi ²
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	22	0.033	0.0011	0	0.000	0.0000
<i>Alchonea laxiflora</i>	8	0.012	0.0001	0	0.000	0.0000
<i>Althananthera sessilis</i>	16	0.024	0.0576	12	0.010	0.0001
<i>Asystacia gangentica</i>	40	0.607	0.3684	32	0.026	0.0007
<i>Axonopus compressus</i>	84	0.128	0.0168	58	0.047	0.0022
<i>Chromolaena odorata</i>	2	0.003	0.0000	0	0.000	0.0000
<i>Cnetis ferruginea</i>	2	0.003	0.0001	2	0.002	0.0000
<i>Combretum hispidum</i>	2	0.003	0.0000	0	0.000	0.0000
<i>Commelina diffusa</i>	8	0.012	0.0001	10	0.008	0.6707
<i>Ficus exasperata</i>	2	0.033	0.0001	6	0.005	0.0000
<i>Ipomoea sp.</i>	64	0.097	0.0940	28	0.023	0.0053
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	12	0.018	0.0003	0	0.000	0.0000
<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	54	0.082	0.0067	84	0.068	0.0046
<i>Panicum maximum</i>	34	0.052	0.0027	0	0.000	0.0000
<i>Sida acuta</i>	8	0.012	0.0011	0	0.000	0.0000
<i>Tridax procumbens</i>	300	0.456	0.2079	998	0.811	0.6577
16	658		0.6752	1230		0.6707

SAIGON:

Diversity, $D = 1/\sum P_i^2 = 1/0.6752 = 1.481$

Equitability, $E_D = D/D_{MAX} = 1.481/16 = 0.093$

EDWARD:

Diversity, $D = 1/\sum P_i^2 = 1/0.6707 = 1.491$

Equitability, $E_D = D/D_{MAX} = 1.491/9 = 0.167$

Equitability ranges from 0 to 1, with 1 being complete evenness (Siemann, *et al.*, 1997).

Table 4: Effect of distance from the base of the sampled on number of weeds, fresh weight and dry weight of weeds.

Distance(m)	EDWARD			SAIGON		
	No of weeds	Fresh weight (g)	Dry weight(g)	No of weeds	Fresh weight (g)	Dry weight (g)
1	26.33a	221.10a	44.83a	49.333a	367.37a	47.067a
2	24.24a	177.83a	37.70a	45ab	299.10b	37.467ab
3	23.33a	146.67a	32.00a	44.667ab	290.93b	33.667b
4	22.00a	78.50a	21.05a	38.333ab	248.00c	33.017b
5	16.33a	72.47a	20.13a	29.667b	182.97d	22.967c

Means followed by the same letter in a column are not significantly different by DMRT at 5% level of probability.

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Corresponding Author

Adeoye, P. O.

National Horticultural Research Institute, P. M. B. 5432, Idi-Ishin, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Email: hispresence01@yahoo.com